

BIOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF MAN

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Annotation: Through the following article, students will have information about the human body, human body parts, its external and internal structure, the movement of internal organs, breathing, reproduction, movement and blood circulation systems in a way appropriate for their age. Many pictures and information on the subject are given in the textbook.

Basic concepts: skeleton, organ, organ system, cycle, kidney, chest, spine, artery, vein, small intestine, spinal cord.

In the 3rd grade "Natural Science" textbook, the section "Human structure" is given, and the section consists of the topics "Human body, skin and skeleton" and "Human brain, digestive organs and lungs". Each topic is divided into plans in its place. The best method for passing these topics is demonstration and practicality. The textbook mainly contains many pictures.

These will help students to develop more understanding, and their imagination will be more

112-rasm.
Odam yuragi.

114-rasm.
Odam miyasi:
1 – bosh miya;
2 – orqa miya.

116-rasm. Odam
o'phasi.

clear and correct. Textbook information is explained to students based on pictures, and videos and slides are used to make the lesson more interesting. In this case, information suitable for the age of students, that is, not too complicated, is given.

A game is held to check that students know the human external organs well and that they act consciously. In this, the teacher takes several (10-12) students to the blackboard and asks them to show some part of the body. says, but he shows another body part. It is tested whether the students show the body parts shown by the teacher or consciously show the body parts they have heard. The student who shows the part of the body that the teacher did not show, leaves the game, and the student who remains at the end is the winner.

Didactic game "Jamlanma".

Students are divided into 3 groups. Each group is given papers with individual body parts and a picture of the human body.

For example, group 1 will be given the following task: Find the main internal organs of a person and place them correctly. They are given papers with the following body parts written on them: tongue, lungs, stomach, esophagus, liver, heart, arm bones, intestines. They find the main internal organs of a person and glue them according to the order of placement on the picture of a person.

Group 2: Collect the human skeleton: heart, skull, leg bones, intestines, chest, spine, arm bones, throat, pelvis.

Group 3: Digestive organs: spine, stomach, lungs, mouth, tongue, small intestine, chest, large intestine, throat, esophagus, liver.

After all 3 groups have fulfilled the condition, each group will comment on the board, and the

110-rasm. Odamning asosiy ichki a'zolari:
1 – yurak;
2 – o'pka;
3 – jigar;
4 – oshqozon;
5 – ichaklar.

111-rasm. Odam skeleti: 1 – bosh suyagi;
2 – umurtqa pog'onasi;
3 – ko'krak qafasi;
4 – to's suyagi;
5 – qo'l suyaklari;
6 – oyoq suyaklari.

115-rasm. Hazm qilish a'zolari:
1 – og'iz va til;
2 – tomoq;
3 – qizilo'ngach;
4 – oshqozon;
5 – ingichka ichak;
6 – yo'g'on ichak.

projector will show pictures like the ones above. The students will find out whether they have fulfilled the condition correctly or incorrectly. are evaluated.

Through both games, students learn the arrangement of body parts.

Conclusion: In conclusion, through the information in the textbook, students learn about their body, its organs, their activities, manage their body, exercise it, and improve the functioning of their organs. They will also gain knowledge about the internal and external organs of a person, the factors that negatively affect them, and the prevention of diseases.

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